

Near infrared technique as a tool for the rapid assessment of waste wood quality for energy applications

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ABSTRACT

Considering the focus of the current European policy in promoting the reuse of waste products and increasing the share of renewable energies, waste wood is becoming an appealing resource rather than a product to dispose of. End-life waste wood products could be used for the production of panel board or as feedstock in combustion units. In this study, waste wood samples have been collected in a big panel board company, and have been analyzed by means of Near Infrared Spectroscopy. Principal Component Analysis has been used in order to investigate the variability of the material, and Partial-Least Squares regression models have been developed for the prediction of moisture content and net calorific value. The results indicate that both models could be used in quality control applications, and Near Infrared Spectroscopy can be considered as a tool for the rapid evaluation of waste wood parameters for energy applications. Considering the high correlation between the two parameters it is also possible to analyze only the moisture content and have indications about the net calorific value using a simple linear regression, with positive effects in terms of quality control and the reuse of the waste wood material.

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1. Introduction

The promotion and reuse of waste products are getting increasing attention in the current European policy. The Waste Framework Directive - 2008/98/EC [1] sets the basis for the waste management and defines the waste, recycling and recovery, explaining when a waste becomes a secondary raw-material. Wood material can be used for different purposes, e.g. bio-chemicals, bioenergy and the industrial sectors. The big advantage is related to the full renewability and wide reuse and recyclability of the material, so it can be utilized several times before the end-life [2].

End-life waste wood products could be used for panel board production or as feedstock in combustion units or, if not possible, be sent to the disposal. This is in line with the renewable energy policy that favors the use of non-fossil material. In fact, European energy and climate policies aim at decreasing the emission of greenhouse gasses in the atmosphere to reduce global warming and climate change. Wood could have a big role in this, as biomass has reached the highest percentage among the different sources of renewable share as a source of energy [3,4]. It should, though, be

considered that wood is a limited resource and is used in different sectors beside the energy use, e.g. paper and construction [2]. Instead, a large amount of end-life wood products currently remain unused [5,6], and the utilization of waste wood in combustion units is more favorable than virgin wood for climate change mitigation [7].

Waste wood management depends mainly on the policies in the different countries. The material could be used for particleboard production, recycled for wood composite or bioenergy production, based on the different waste wood categories established [8]. In the case of bioenergy production, the use of solid biofuels is regulated by a series of technical standards EN ISO 17225 that set their quality based on different chemical and physical parameters and quality attributes as the origin of the biomass. Chemically treated wood is also included in the origin of the biomass, but paints, preservatives, coatings and adhesives could by combustion release toxic air substances, harmful for the environment and human health [9]. However, these emissions could be avoided using gas cleaning in combustion plants. In addition, in some European countries, slightly treated waste wood materials could be used in CHP production plants, while in others it is not allowed [5,10].

It is well known that waste wood material comes from different sources, e.g. industrial and commercial sectors, construction and demolition activities, and, as a consequence, it is very

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heterogeneous and presents a high variation in sample properties [5,11]. The knowledge of waste wood variability and composition is of great importance for enhancing its reuse and deciding its suitability for energy applications.

Two of the most important parameters to assess are moisture content and net calorific value. Moisture content depends on several factors: season, species, storage conditions and presence/absence of some tree parts as leaves or needles [12,13]. It is a crucial parameter as it causes the reduction of the net calorific value due to the amount of energy needed for the vaporization process [14,15]. In addition, it is a driving factor for the optimization of the transportation costs along all the supply chain as transport efficiency is penalized by high moisture content [16]. Net calorific value defines the energy content of the biofuel, and influences the planning and control of the thermal systems [17].

The chemical and physical characteristics of waste wood material to be used for energy applications have already been investigated in several studies [5,6,11,18,19]. Some authors focused their attention on the concerns about emissions from combustion of waste wood [9], others to the reduction of carbon footprint with respect to virgin wood combustion [7,20]. To our knowledge only a limited number of studies has been carried out on the use of Near Infrared Spectroscopy (NIRS) for the investigation of the variation in chemical-physical parameters of waste wood samples. Near Infrared (NIR) hyperspectral imaging was investigated by Maurusch et al. to detect chemical preservatives and plastic contaminants in wood [21]. Visible image processing has been used to sort wood according to type, color and quality grades [22–24]. Sensor technologies have also been tested for the identification of specific contaminants (e.g. chromium-based contaminants, preservatives and wood plastic composites) in mixed wood materials [25]. Differently from waste wood, the application of NIRS for the prediction of chemical-physical parameters of different biomass sources has been widely investigated with good results [26].

In this study waste wood samples have been collected in a panel board company located in the Northern part of Italy during two days of sampling with two aims: i) investigate the variability of waste wood and ii) develop regression models for the prediction of moisture content and net calorific value. The first aim is essential in order to achieve the second aim with good prediction performance, taking into account the described variability.

As a consequence, the samples have been analyzed by NIRS directly in the panel board company, and afterwards as they arrive in the lab, and the variation in material composition among the different lots have been investigated using Principal Component Analysis (PCA). As the aim of our study is to investigate the variability of the lots, and not the seasonal variability, we deemed it sufficient to measure several lots across two days in February 2020. Partial-Least Squares regression (PLS) models have been developed for predicting the moisture content and net calorific value of the samples. As a final step, the correlation between the two parameters has been investigated.

First indications about the variability and the chemical-physical characteristics of the material are essential for determining the suitability in energy applications. The secondary aim is essential to improve the best selection of the final use of the waste wood material with positive effects in terms of health and environmental, as well as economic issues.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Collection of waste wood samples

The waste wood samples have been collected in a panel board company located in the Northern part of Italy during two days of

sampling (February 18–19th, 2020). The weather conditions during the sampling were stable with temperature and humidity around 11 °C and 95%, respectively, and no rain. The waste wood material arrived at the company by trucks from different recycling centers located in the whole country. It is mainly composed by packaging, old furniture, and construction and demolition materials.

As the material is composed of different types of wood material and arrived from different locations the heterogeneity is high. In order to maintain sample representativeness, the sampling methodology followed is based on the technical standard EN ISO 18135:2017 – Sampling of solid biofuels. The sampling is located in a first step of the production chain, i.e. after a first cleaning (removal of stone, iron and other heavy materials by washing) and grinding (particle size of the material reduced to around 5 cm). Specifically, the former operation consists in immersing the incoming waste wood material in water and removing all the material that sinks (non-wood material are heavier than waste wood). Only waste wood containing a high quantity of undesired non-wood material (based on visual inspection) undergoes this additional cleaning step before entering the panel board production process.

In detail, the production stream has been loaded every hour in an external unloading tank in order to create a static lot. A total of 24 randomly distributed increments have been collected from each of the 16 lots using a sampling scoop (taking around 10 L of material), resulting in a total of 384 samples, i.e. 16 lots \times 24 increments (we note these DT-Sam_{tot}). All the samples have been analyzed by NIRS directly on site. In addition, four of the 24 increments for each lot - resulting in a total of 64 samples - have been sent to the lab in hermetically sealed plastic bags for the traditional lab analysis and another round of NIR analysis (DT-Lab). The DT-Sam_{tot} samples have furthermore been divided into a subset of the four increments that were measured both at the panel board company and in the laboratory, denoted as DT-Sam_{red}. This enables us to have more accurate indications about the differences in variability between DT-Lab and DT-Sam_{tot} samples. Please note that all the samples have been analyzed after the waste wood has gone through a sorting process, i.e. removing all non-wood material before NIR and lab analyses. A graphical representation of the working procedure is reported in Fig. 1.

2.2. Moisture content analysis

Lab analysis was carried out on DT-Lab samples using the European technical standards on solid biofuels. In detail, moisture content (M) was determined by drying around 300 g of material at 105 ± 2 °C in air atmosphere using a forced ventilation oven (mod. M120-VF, MPM Instruments). When constant mass is achieved, the percentage of moisture content was calculated as the loss in mass of the sample as reported in the following equation:

$$M = \frac{(m_2 - m_3)}{(m_2 - m_1)} \times 100$$

M = moisture content as received (%);

m_1 = weight of the empty tray (g);

m_2 = combined weight of the tray and the sample before drying (g);

m_3 = combined weight of the tray and the sample after drying (g).

All the waste wood samples have been analyzed in duplicate and the analysis was carried out according to EN ISO 18134–2.

Fig. 1. Scheme of the working procedure. 16 lots were measured by NIRS at 24 increments each, where four of the increments were sent to the laboratory for further analysis. A reduced set of NIR measurements from the original 16 x 24 samples has been created, only including the four increments that also were sent to the laboratory. The small NIR instrument is shown both by the waste wood pile from the panel board company, as well as from the laboratory.

2.3. Sample preparation

The samples preparation has been carried out using the technical standard UNI 15443. The procedure consists of: i) sampling/reducing the material by means of a quartering process, ii) stabilizing the sample for at least 24 h not exceeding 40 °C and iii) grinding it to below 1 mm of particle size using a cutting mill (mod. SM 2000, RETSCH). Before the grinding process the metallic items (e.g. nails or staples) and non-wood materials (e.g. glass, plastic, paper) were removed. The ground material was used for the following lab analysis.

2.4. Net calorific value analysis

The net calorific value (NCV) was determined according to EN ISO 18125. The procedure consists in burning the samples by means of an isoperibolic bomb calorimeter (mod. C2000 basic, IKA) in high-pressure oxygen atmosphere. The calibration of the calorimeter has been performed burning a certified benzoic acid standard (IKA Benzoic Acid C723) under the same analysis conditions as for the wood samples. The net calorific value was calculated by subtracting the amount of heat required to evaporate the water contained in the sample as reported in the following equation:

$$NCV = NCV_{dr} \times \left(\frac{100 - M_{ar}}{100} \right) - 24.43 \times M_{ar}$$

NCV = net calorific value as received (J/g) with moisture content M_{ar} ;

NCV_{dr} = net calorific value on a dry basis (J/g);

M_{ar} = moisture content as received (%);

24.43 = correction factor for the enthalpy of vaporization for moisture at a temperature of 25 °C per 1% of moisture (J/g).

2.5. Near-infrared data

Spectra have been collected using a MicroNIR™ OnSite instrument distributed by Viavi Solutions Inc. (JDSU Corporation, Milpitas, USA). The instrument consists of two vacuum tungsten lamps

as radiation sources and a linear-variable filter (LVF) as dispersing element directly connected to a 128 pixel indium gallium arsenide (InGaAs) photodiode array detector. The spectra acquisition was performed in reflectance mode, in the spectral region 950–1650 nm, with an integration time of 6.7 ms and at a nominal spectral resolution of 6.25 nm. Each spectrum was the average of 100 scans. Every 10 min a dark reference (total absorbance) and a blank spectrum (total reflectance) using Spectralon have been acquired to remove instrumental and environmental drift effects. Both DT-Sam_{Tot} and DT-Lab were measured by this procedure (please note that DT-Sam_{Red} is a subset of DT-Sam_{Tot}). In detail, at the panel board company a total of ten measurements have been collected for each of the 24 increments for each of the 16 lots. In the lab a total of ten measurements have been collected for each of the two sample replicates before the moisture content analysis, resulting in a total of 20 measurements for each sample, repeated for each of the four increments for each of the 16 lots. As one of the main aims is the development of regression models for the prediction of moisture content and net calorific value, the samples have been analyzed prior to any other lab analysis, with their original moisture content as they had during collection at the panel board company.

All the spectra have been acquired with the MicroNIR Pro software (JDSU Corporation, Milpitas, USA) and transferred to Matlab (Mathworks, Natick, USA).

2.6. Multivariate data analysis

PCA was performed both on DT-Sam_{Tot}, DT-Sam_{Red} and DT-Lab datasets in order to get qualitative information about the variability of the waste wood composition between the different lots and the number of increments for each lot. NIR absorbance values of the waste wood samples have been pre-processed using Standard Normal Variate (SNV) [27] in order to reduce physical effects. Finally, the samples have been averaged across the NIR measurements to increase the signal-to-noise-ratio. Confidence ellipses have been computed based on the scores of a local PCA (based on the scores from the original PCA), in order to get an indication about the variability of each lot. The centre of each ellipse is the mean score values and the radius of the ellipse the standard error of each variability direction. The two first PCA loadings have been investigated to understand the compounds/wavelengths responsible for

the separation of the waste wood samples in the scores space.

PLS was calculated in order to predict the moisture content, M, and net calorific value, NCV, of waste wood samples. Before model computation different pre-processing techniques - including SNV, Multiplicative Scatter Correction (MSC), first and second derivative (Savitzky-Golay [28] with 9 or 13 smoothing points and 2nd order polynomial) - were applied to the spectral dataset to reduce baseline shift and scatter effects [29]. The models were developed on DT-Lab samples and were validated using venetian blind-cross validation (with samples sorted according to reference method using five segments, and keeping replicates together in the same segment). Considering the high heterogeneity of the material (both because of the different types of waste wood and locations) this cross-validation ensures that the PLS models were developed taking into consideration all the waste wood variability and not only a single type of waste wood category or a single lot.

The final PLS model was subsequently used to predict the moisture content and net calorific value of the DT-Sam_{Tot} (and DT-Sam_{Red}) measurements taken onsite. This was useful to figure out how the prediction is behaving, and to understand the variability of each lot. The best prediction models have been evaluated taking into account several figures of merit: the coefficient of determination (R^2), Root Mean Square Error of Cross Validation (RMSECV), slope and the ratio of standard error of prediction to standard deviation (RPD).

As a final consideration, due to the high correlation of the data in this study, a linear regression has been computed for the prediction of net calorific value (dependent variable) from moisture content (independent variable) by using a linear equation. This was performed in order to investigate if in practice is sufficient to only measure the moisture content, and through this get an estimate of the net calorific value. A driving force here is that the reference analysis for moisture content is simpler and cheaper than the corresponding for the net calorific value, and it is easier and faster to maintain one PLS model rather than two.

All computations were performed in Matlab (ver. MATLAB R2019b, The MathWorks) using in-house functions based on existing algorithms.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Spectra

Fig. 2 reports the mean spectrum for each lot of DT-Lab samples colored according to the mean moisture content (Fig. 2a) and mean net calorific value (Fig. 2b) of each lot. As it can be noted the spectra are ordered according to the moisture content and net calorific value, but with opposite trend, i.e. the lot with the highest moisture content has the highest absorbance, while the lot with highest net calorific value has the lowest absorbance. This is in correspondence with the negative correlation between net calorific value and moisture content reported earlier [30]; samples with a high moisture content will have a low net calorific value. This is also confirmed by the highest peak at 1459 nm, located in the absorption band of OH stretching [31]. It should, though, be noted that the mean spectrum of lot 1 has a deviating trend.

3.2. Traditional lab analysis

A general descriptive statistic of the moisture content and net calorific value has been carried out. Regarding moisture content the 64 waste wood samples analyzed have an average of 29.2%, standard deviation = 8.6%, max value = 46.1% and min value = 15.2%, resulting in a range = 30.8%. Regarding net calorific value the samples have an average of 12041.5 J/g, standard

deviation = 1779.7 J/g, max value = 15328.0 J/g and min value = 8596.0 J/g, resulting in a range = 6732.0 J/g. The samples show a relatively high variability in moisture due to the different waste wood material processed in the panel board industry. Waste wood with a higher percentage of non-wood material is subjected to a preliminary step of cleaning consisting in a washing operation. The remaining material enters, instead, directly into the production process.

Fig. 3 reports a general descriptive statistic of the moisture content and net calorific value for each lot. The horizontal red line is the mean value, while the whiskers represent the max and min values for each lot. As it can be noted in Fig. 3a, the lot with the highest variability is lot 13. Lots with lower values of moisture content are lots 1 and 11, while lot 4 has the highest moisture content. Lot 9 has the widest range between max and min values. As a last note, lot 11 shows an outlier value, but also the lowest variability, and it is thus likely that this is more an indication of natural variability than an actual measurement outlier. The net calorific values reported in Fig. 3b show an opposite trend, i.e. lots with high moisture content have low net calorific value. Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) was calculated and it confirmed that the net calorific value is highly negative correlated with moisture content ($r = -0.99$). Consequently, the discussion of the successive results will refer only to the moisture content, since the net calorific value will have the opposite trend.

3.3. PCA of DT-Lab

A PCA has been computed on the SNV pre-processed DT-Lab dataset. Fig. 4a shows the PCA scores plot colored in accordance to the different lots. As it can be noted there are some groupings in the distribution of the waste wood samples among the different lots.

To better investigate the differences, confidence ellipses were calculated using the standard error of each lot (Fig. 4b). The PCA score plot of the two first PCs shows how samples are located in the positive/negative scores of PC1 based on their moisture content/net calorific value. Lots 1, 11, 15 and 16 are located in the negative part of PC1 and also present low values of moisture. Lot 13 has both high and low values of moisture, resulting in an elongated ellipse. All the other lots are located in the positive part of PC1 due to high moisture content. This is also confirmed by the results reported in Fig. 3. Finally, it is interesting to note that the size of the ellipses is proportionate to the moisture content/net calorific value variability of each lot: i.e. the larger the size of the ellipse, the higher the variability in moisture/net calorific value (see Fig. 3).

The two first PCA loadings were investigated in order to find which wavelengths are responsible for the distribution of the lots in the PCA scores plot (Fig. 5). The first loading shows a peak at 1410 nm and, as confirmed by Schwanninger et al. [31], it is related to the 1st overtone of O–H stretching of water. This confirms the outcomes of PCA score plot and underlines how the first loading is affected by the moisture content variability among the lots. On the other hand, the second loading shows peaks at 1360 nm and 1676 nm, corresponding to the 2nd overtone of C–H stretching and C–H deformation and 1st overtone of C–H stretching, respectively. It probably indicates differences in the wood composition of the materials.

3.4. PCA of DT-Sam_{Tot} and DT-Sam_{Red}

In order to investigate whether the variation in sample composition changes according to the number of increments, PCA was also performed on the DT-Sam_{Tot} and on the DT-Sam_{Red} datasets. Please note that the DT-Sam_{Red} dataset includes the same samples as DT-Lab, just measured in two different locations (at the

Fig. 2. Mean spectrum for each of the 16 lots of DT-Lab samples colored in accordance to A) the mean moisture content and B) the mean net calorific value of each lot.

factory site and in the laboratory). This is particularly important for obtaining indications about the optimal sampling procedure in terms of frequency of sampling and number of replicates to perform.

The data have been pre-processed with SNV before PCA computation and ellipses were calculated based on a local PCA on the scores using the standard error of each lot. Fig. 6a shows the PCA score plot of DT-Sam_{Tot} samples. As for DT-Lab, PC1 divides lots in the PCA space based on their moisture content. Lots with low values of moisture, i.e. lot 1, 11, 13, 15 and 16 are located in the negative part of PC1, while lots with high values of moisture are located in the positive part of PC1.

Fig. 6b shows the PCA score plot of DT-Sam_{Red} samples. Once again, PC1 is responsible for the separation of the samples based on their moisture content. The location of the lots in the PCA score plot is similar to Fig. 6a, but with some differences in the distribution and the size of the ellipses. Lot 13 is the lot with the largest spread in PCA space, as in Fig. 4b, which also was expected, as the only difference between these two sample sets is the location the NIR analysis was performed.

The size of the ellipses has been calculated for each lot and for the three different datasets to have indications about the variability of the lots and how it is changing increasing the number of the increments (Fig. 7). As it can be noted the ellipse size results to be the smallest for DT-Sam_{Tot}, while it is similar for DT-Lab and DT-Sam_{Red}. This is in line with our expectations since DT-Sam_{Tot} contains the NIR analysis of all the 24 increments, while DT-Lab and DT-Sam_{Red} only include four of the 24 increments. In other words, as DT-Sam_{Tot} includes more scans than DT-Sam_{Red}, the estimate of the standard error will also be smaller, as long as the variability within the two sample sets are similar. The latter two datasets show some differences in the variability of the lots. This is probably

related to the fact that DT-Lab samples have been analyzed in duplicate in the lab (20 NIR measurements), while DT-Sam_{Red} samples only once at the panel board company (10 NIR measurements).

The loading plot of PCA on DT-Sam_{Tot} and DT-Sam_{Red} has been investigated to figure out the wavelengths responsible for the distribution of the lots in the PCA space. The first loading of both PCA has two main peaks at 1414 and 1447 nm (data not shown). The first one is assigned to the 1st overtone of O–H stretching of water, while the second is assigned to the 1st overtone of O–H stretching of lignin [31], confirming that the variability in each lot is highly affected by the variability in moisture content.

3.5. PLS models

The PLS models for the prediction of moisture content and net calorific value were developed using the DT-Lab dataset. Different pre-processing techniques have been applied to the spectral data as mentioned in section 2.6.

For the prediction model of moisture content the 10 NIR measurements of each replicate sample were averaged across the replicates before computation. The dataset consists now of 128 (64 samples x 2 replicates) x 125 wavelengths. The regression models were validated using venetian blind-cross validation (5 segments) keeping the two replicates in the same cancellation group.

Table 1 reports the PLS prediction results for moisture content (please note that all datasets have been mean-centered as a final pre-processing step). Two models have been selected as the best ones: no pre-processing and using the second derivative Savitzky-Golay with second-order polynomial and 9-points window. Because of the coarse particle size of the material and the presence of scattering in the spectra the second derivative Savitzky-Golay

Fig. 3. General descriptive statistic of A) moisture content and B) net calorific value for each of the 16 lots. The blue boxes indicate the variability inside the upper and lower quartiles. The horizontal red line is the mean value, while the whiskers represent the max and min values for each lot, the red cross is an outlier value.

Fig. 4. PCA score plot of DT-Lab samples A) colored according to the different lot; B) with standard error ellipses for each lot instead of the individual score values.

Fig. 5. Two first loadings of the PCA on DT-Lab samples, shown in Fig. 4. The vertical lines shows the interpretation of three important wavelengths (1410 nm is water, while the two lines at 1360 and 1676 nm are due to difference in the chemical composition of the materials).

model has been selected as the best. This model also has a notable lower model complexity (three vs. six latent variables), and thus it is assumed to be more robust.

The developed prediction model had $R^2 = 0.98$, $RMSECV = 1.34\%$ and $RPD = 6.82$, indicating the development of a model that could be used as a tool for any quality control applications, which also is according to how Williams [32] interpreted the RPD value.

The authors are aware that the moisture content of the samples depends on several factors and can vary depending on the sample size. As already mentioned, the NIR analysis has been performed on samples collected under real industrial conditions and with a particle size of around 5 cm. We assume that new samples have similar

Fig. 6. PCA score plot with standard error ellipses for each lot considering (A) all the samples of DT-Sam_{Tot} and (B) only four of the 24 increments for each lot that have been sent to the lab (DT-Sam_{Red}).

Fig. 7. Ellipses size of the 16 lots for the three different datasets.

particle size and distribution of water. The developed model does not show a perfect fit, but the slight bias did not indicate to be a problem for new predictions.

Since we only have one reference value per sample for the net calorific value, the 20 NIR measurements were averaged across the replicates before the computation of the prediction model. The dataset thus consists of 64 samples x 125 wavelengths. The regression models were, again, validated using venetian blind-cross validation (5 segments).

Table 2 reports the PLS prediction results for the net calorific value. The strongest NCV prediction model was, again, developed using second derivative Savitzky-Golay with second-order polynomial and 9-points window. The prediction model was developed

Table 1

Summary of PLS results for moisture content (%).

Pre-treatment	n	LVs	R ²	RMSECV (%)	slope	RPD
Mean	128	6	0.98	1.27	0.9686	6.76
SNV	128	4	0.95	1.91	0.934	4.50
MSC	126	4	0.94	2.06	0.9254	4.17
9der1	128	2	0.96	1.65	0.9498	5.21
13der1	128	2	0.96	1.73	0.9458	4.97
9der2	128	3	0.98	1.34	0.9658	6.41
13der2	128	3	0.97	1.41	0.9629	6.09

The best model is highlighted in bold. SNV: standard normal variate; MSC: Multiplicative Scatter Correction; xder1: first derivative with x number of smoothing points; xder2: second derivative with x number of smoothing points; n: number of samples; LVs: number of latent variables; R²: squared correlation coefficient; RMSECV: root-mean-squared-error of cross-validation; slope: slope of the regression line between the actual vs. predicted values; RPD: ratio of standard error of prediction to standard deviation.

using two LVs and had R² = 0.94, RMSECV = 414.65 J/g, and RPD = 4.29. According to Williams [32], prediction models with RPD values between three and five can be used for screening applications.

Fig. 8 shows the regression plot of observed versus fitted response for moisture content (Fig. 8a) and net calorific value models (Fig. 8b).

The regression coefficient plot of the two PLS regression models selected as the best ones were investigated in order to figure out the most relevant wavelengths for the prediction of the two parameters (Fig. 9). As it can be noted the two lines have a mirror-trend confirming the highly negative correlation between moisture content and net calorific value. The prediction of net calorific value is mainly linked to O–H bonds of water, but also to C–H bonds (more energetic than others type of bonds). The relationship to the O–H bonds of water is natural due to the already mentioned and well know negative correlation with the moisture content [30,33]. As mentioned, the moisture prediction is based on the opposite trend, and thus again, mainly linked to the O–H bonds of water [34,35].

Table 2
Summary of PLS results for net calorific value (J/g).

Pre-treatment	n	LVs	R ²	RMSECV (J/g)	slope	RPD
Mean	64	4	0.94	434.03	0.9476	4.10
SNV	64	2	0.93	479.64	0.9319	3.71
MSC	64	4	0.91	526.91	0.9169	3.38
9der1	64	2	0.93	458.22	0.9428	3.88
13der1	64	2	0.93	468.54	0.9401	3.80
9der2	64	2	0.94	414.65	0.9515	4.29
13der2	64	2	0.94	432.34	0.9519	4.12

The best model is highlighted in bold. SNV: standard normal variate; MSC: Multiplicative Scatter Correction; xder1: first derivative with x number of smoothing points; xder2: second derivative with x number of smoothing points; n: number of samples; LVs: number of latent variables; R²: squared correlation coefficient; RMSECV: root-mean-squared-error of cross-validation; slope: slope of the regression line between the actual vs. predicted values; RPD: ratio of standard error of prediction to standard deviation.

The most important wavelengths are located at 1373 nm and 1410 nm. The former is assigned to the 1st overtone C–H stretching and C–H deformation, while the latter is located to the area of 1st overtone O–H stretching of water [31].

To have indications about the prediction performance of the developed models, DT-Sam_{Tot} and DT-Sam_{Red} datasets were used as test sets. We are aware that we are predicting the same samples analyzed in two different locations, i.e. the panel board industry and the lab, but the outcomes are useful for investigating how the variability and prediction results vary changing the number of increments and if it has an influence in the development of successive models. We subsequently averaged the predictions in order to get one value per lot. Fig. 10 shows the measured moisture content and net calorific value and the predicted moisture content and net calorific value using DT-Sam_{Tot} and DT-Sam_{Red} as test sets. The predicted values of DT-Sam_{Red} samples are in most of the cases closer to the reference values, so the variation in moisture content and net calorific values of the 24 increments of DT-Sam_{Tot} is larger

than the variation of the four samples of DT-Sam_{Red}. However, the difference between the three different values for each lot are always fairly small, indicating that the four collected increments, and the corresponding replicates and scans are able to describe the variability between the lots.

3.6. Linear regression

Fig. 9 suggests a good correlation between the PLS regression coefficients of moisture content and net calorific value. In fact, the coefficient of correlation between the regression coefficients is as high as R² = 0.93. In addition, considering the high negative correlation between moisture content and net calorific value, a linear regression has been computed trying to model the relationship between the two parameters by fitting a linear equation. Net calorific value has been used as dependent variable and moisture content as independent variable. The estimation of NCV can be carried out as reported in the equation below:

$$NCV (J/g) = a + b * M (\%),$$

where a = 18040.071; b = -205.195.

The coefficient of multiple correlation (R² = 0.97) confirmed the good correlation. We used this equation on the cross-validated moisture predictions from Table 1, and this gave us an R² of 0.95, slightly higher than the direct PLS model (see Table 2), but still confirming that this approach gives a good performance. However, this only holds as long as the correlation between moisture at the net calorific value is similar in future samples [36,37]. The results are promising and can support the energy valorization of the waste wood material. This indicates that sector operators could analyze only the moisture content and have indications also about the net calorific value. This would simplify model maintenance as only one regression model would need to be maintained, while still improving the quality control and the best reuse of the material.

Fig. 8. Regression plot of observed versus fitted response for A) moisture content and B) net calorific value. The data of both models have been pre-processed by a second order derivation using the Savitzky-Golay algorithm with 9 smoothing points and a second order polynomial fitting. Note that the slope given in Tables 1 and 2 refer to the slope of the trendline (red) in this figure.

Fig. 9. Regression coefficient (B) plot of PLS models for the prediction of moisture content (blue line) and net calorific value (orange line). The two vertical lines refer to the two most important wavelengths: 1373 nm assigned to the 1st overtone of C–H stretching and C–H deformation, and 1410 assigned to the 1st overtone of O–H stretching of water.

Fig. 10. A) measured moisture content (blue line) and predicted moisture content using DT-Sam_{Tot} (orange line) and DT-Sam_{Red} (yellow line) as test sets; B) measured net calorific value (blue line) and predicted net calorific value using DT-Sam_{Tot} (orange line) and DT-Sam_{Red} (yellow line) as test sets.

4. Conclusions

Waste wood samples collected in a big panel board company located in the Northern part of Italy have been analyzed by means of a hand-held NIR spectrophotometer directly on-site and later in the lab, with the aim to get knowledge about the waste wood variability and composition. This is of great importance for increasing the reuse of the material and decide the suitability for energy applications. The variation in material composition has been investigated using PCA. It shows that samples are located in the scores space based on their moisture content/net calorific value

and the size of the ellipses is proportionate to the relative variability of these attributes within each lot.

Two of the most important parameters for energy assessment of waste wood material, i.e. moisture content and net calorific value, have been analyzed and PLS regression models have been developed for the rapid assessment of the waste wood and investigate the suitability of the material for energy applications. Both models could be used for quality control applications; in detail the prediction model for moisture content has RMSECV = 1.34% and R² = 0.98, while the prediction model for net calorific value has RMSECV = 414.65 J/g and R² = 0.94. In addition, considering the

high negative correlation between the two parameters, a linear regression has been computed for the prediction of net calorific value from moisture content. The results showed that it is possible to analyze only the moisture content and have indications about the net calorific value. This is a strong-point for improving the quality control and the energy valorization of the waste wood material.

NIR spectroscopy coupled with multivariate data analysis demonstrated to be a promising tool for investigating the variability of the material and have indications about the procedure to perform in order to overcome the sampling problems of high heterogeneous materials. In addition, it allows obtaining a rapid characterization of the waste wood materials for energy applications. Hence, spectroscopy has the possibility for the real-time quality control of the product and for tuning the combustion devices based on the characteristics of the waste wood supplied. Future applications could be carried out investigating the use of multispectral analysis and to correlate NIR spectra with additional chemical parameters of waste wood material (i.e. carbon, lignin, nitrogen and ash content). This will lead to an even more precise information about the waste wood characteristics and it is essential for the most appropriate energy application of the material and for the limitation of the related environmental problems.

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CRediT authorship contribution statement

M. Mancini: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Resources, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Funding acquisition. **Å. Rinnan:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Resources, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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